

Agro2Circular

D5.8 – Plastics end of life scenarios

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Authors: Pedro López (CETEC); Alejandro Arribas (CETEC), María Mondéjar (CETEC)

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1 List of abbreviations

Al	Aluminium
CETEC	Centro Tecnológico del Calzado y del Plástico
EVA	Ethylen vinyl acetate
EVOH	Ethylen vinyl alcohol
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
PA	Polyamide
PBAT	Polybutylene adipate terephthalate
PHBV	Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-hydroxyvalerate)
TOC	Total organic carbon
RPM	Revolutions per minute
TM	Melting temperature
PM	Melting pressure
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
BOD	Biological oxygen demand

2 Executive summary

Recycled material formulations from aseptic bags and agricultural plastics, developed in task 5.2 have been subjected to a successive recycling process to ensure their continued use in the recycling cycle. This study has ensured, through the mechanical and rheological properties, that the formulations developed can be used without problems for at least five recycling cycles.

Furthermore, the developed formulations of biodegradable polymers obtained from the fermentation process of task 5.1.2 PHBV and carotenoids production by *Haloferax mediterranei* cell factory and the commercial materials such as PBAT and a mixture of starch and PBAT (PHBV-PBAT1 and PHBV-StarchPBAT1), have been subjected to compostability tests using the UNE EN ISO 14855 standard, biodegradability in soil according to the UNE EN ISO 17556 standard and biodegradability in seawater according to the UNE EN ISO 19679 standard. This compostability and biodegradability study has ensured that the formulations developed with PHBV are compostable and also biodegradable in soil and seawater.

3 Introduction

Recycling plastics is a fundamental pillar of the circular economy. The reuse of these materials, promoted by the different administrations and by the recycling industry itself, is providing new ways of using them and boosting the economy of the sector. One of the objectives of the Agro2Circular project is that all compounds developed from the fermentation process of task 5.1.2 PHBV and carotenoids production must be completely recyclable. To ensure that the formulations developed are recyclable, a series of experiments and tests have been designed that have allowed us to determine that at least the developed materials are capable of being recycled for 5 cycles without suffering a significant loss of properties, making them perfectly reusable as secondary raw material.

On the biodegradable polymers side, Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) copolymer is a microbial polyester presenting the advantages of biodegradability and biocompatibility over other thermoplastics with useful mechanical properties. However, their costs and performances must be adjusted by blending with suitable polymers.

The objective of this project is to increase the proportion of PHBV in blends with other commercial and biodegradable polymers to reduce the material cost and increase the opportunity of being used in as many applications as possible. However, in addition to all this, the formulations developed in the project must be environmentally friendly and not produce undesirable effects such as microplastics. Therefore, all the formulations developed must comply with compostability and biodegradability standards. Specifically, the materials developed will be compostable and biodegradable both in soil and seawater.

Regarding the applications of this project, they will be limited to films for agricultural and food packaging use, without prejudice to the fact that other applications are perfectly possible. Furthermore, we hope that the knowledge generated in this project will be useful in the development of PHBV as a polymer for general use.

4 Plastic end life scenarios

This report will describe the plastic end life scenarios, the part of recyclability for agrofood plastic and the part of biodegradability for the developed PHBV.

4.1 Recyclability

In order to determine the recyclability of the formulations developed in task 5.2 and scaled in task 5.4 (PHBV-PBAT1 and PHBV-StarchPBAT1), they have been subjected to an extrusion process and subsequent injection to obtain test specimens. This process has been repeated 5 times and the mechanical and rheological properties have been determined in each of the 5 stages.

Figure 1: recyclability squeme

To manufacture our composites, the following steps were followed:

- The raw materials were oven-dried at 70°C for four hours to avoid moisture, which causes problems not only during manufacturing but is also a determining factor in the biodegradability process.
- Two different compounds were mixed before extrusion:
 - T1: which contains PHBV from CETBIO and PBAT ecoflex.
 - T2: composed of PHBV from CETBIO and StarchPBAT.
 - Raw materials manufacturers were PHBV from CETBIO and BASF for PBAT ecoflex. StarchPBAT was obtained from Eversia
- Extrusion
- Injection
- Test results.

4.1.1 Extrusion

A Leistritz extruder, model ZSE 18HP, was used to manufacture the two blends. The extruder is characterized by two co-rotating screws that mesh with each other, conjugated. Co-rotating means that the two screws rotate in the same direction, intermeshing means that the screws of one screw penetrate the channels of the other (the distance between the centers of the screws is less than the sum of their radii), and conjugated means that the screws of one screw fit perfectly into the channels of the other.

Figure 2: Leistrizt ZSE 18 HP extruder and feeders

The characteristics of the ZSE 18HP machine are as follows:

Table 1: extruder characteristics

Distance between spindle axes	15 mm
Spindle diameter	17,8 mm
Diameter of the kneading block/disc	17,6 mm
Spindle material	VSA2
Cylinder diameter	18 mm
Cylinder material	VSA2
Spindle length	40 D
Spindle torque	2x35,5Nm

Drive mode	2 d.c. engines in shunt
Drive power	4.7 kW
Maximum motor speed	3000 rpm
Maximum spindle speed	600 rpm
Number of heating zones	8
Heating capacity	7.5 kW
Number of cooling zones	7
Maximum melt pressure	150 Bar

The spindles are modular and fully configurable, allowing to vary as necessary the zones where mixing, shearing or conveying is required.

The extruder can be fed by a pellet and a powder feeder, which has been the one used during the process. The powder feeding was carried out at 0.450 kg/h. It also has a side feeder which was not used on this occasion.

The extruder has 7 heating zones and temperatures have varied from 160 to 175°C, with a melt temperature of 159°C and a melt pressure of 31 bar.

Table 2: extruder parameters

Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4	Z5	Z6	Z7	RPM	TM	Pm
160°C	170°C	175°C	175°C	170°C	165°C	160°C	175°C	159 °C	31 bar

Figure 3: Once the filament comes out of the extruder, it is cooled in a water bath and then passed to the cutter to obtain the pellets.

Figure 4: It was necessary to increase the temperatures by 5 degrees to avoid the appearance of strictions in the yarn.

4.1.2 Injection

Pellets were injected in an Engel injection machine "Victory 200/50 spex" with a maximum closing force of 5000 kN (50 tons). It has no columns, which allows the molding of larger pieces due to a greater interior volume. It has a mold for specimen molding, which allows for the study of the properties of new materials by testing in the CETEC laboratory.

Figure 5: Engel injection machine

The mixture fluidity was not as desired and the mold could not be filled despite increasing the injection pressure. When the temperatures of all the zones were subsequently raised by five degrees, an optimum filling of the mold was achieved. It was essential to preheat the mold to 70°C in order to extract the specimen.

Figure 6: Test specimen mold.

Table 3: Injection parameters

Cooling time	Post-pressure time(s)	Dosing stroke	Mold temperature
12 s	1.25	50 mm	70° C
Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4
175°C	170°C	170°C	170°C

4.2 Characterization

4.2.1 Tensile strength tests

To study the effect on the mechanical properties of the five working cycles, tensile tests were carried out. These were carried out in accordance with the UNE EN ISO 527-2 standard for tensile testing of plastics in the form of specimens. All these tests were carried out using the type 2 specimen model, in accordance with the aforementioned standard. At least 5 tests were carried out per sample, after the samples were first conditioned.

As a result of the tests, stress-strain curve data was collected for the mechanical response for each of the film samples studied.

Table 4: Mechanical properties after 5 cycles of extrusion and injection for the PHBV-PBAT1

SAMPLE PHBV-PBAT1	Tensile strength at break (MPa)	Elongation at Break (MPa)
Cycle 1	17,67±0,75	256±15
Cycle 2	19,51±0,55	256±14
Cycle 3	20,51±1,25	269±25
Cycle 4	18,74±0,29	251±5
Cycle 5	18,47±0,26	256±6

Table 5: Mechanical properties after 5 cycles of extrusion and injection for the PHBV-StarchPBAT1

SAMPLE PHBV-StarchPBAT1	Tensile strength at break (MPa)	Elongation at Break (MPa)
Cycle 1	22,62±0,44	154±4
Cycle 2	22,95±1,01	177±8
Cycle 3	22,33±1,00	187±10
Cycle 4	19,94±0,83	201±5

Cycle 5	22,66±0,74	185±14
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There are no significant differences in the mechanical properties of the material after being subjected to five extrusion and injection cycles. Therefore, based on this outcome, the material can be subjected to at least five cycles without loss of key mechanical properties.

4.2.2 Rheology test

The samples were developed for the project, in the form of blends based on biodegradable thermoplastics. They were to be processed by extrusion methods, and studied by means of rheology tests. In rheology tests, the melt viscosity of the initial formulation with the viscosities of each of the five cycles are compared. In the event of a drop in viscosity, one may conclude that there has been a molecular weight degradation of the material with repeated extrusion and injection processing.

For this purpose, a series of rheology tests were set up, where all were performed for the melted material at 180°C. The temperature value was determined after differential calorimetry studies, seeing that this ensured complete melting of the crystalline structures of the matrix polymers. On this basis, a method was established with floe sweep measurements of the viscosity as a function of the shear rate.

As in the case of mechanical properties, there are no significant differences in the mechanical properties of the material after being subjected to five extrusion and injection cycles. Therefore, if we take into account this criterion, the material can be subjected to at least five cycles without significant loss of properties.

Figure 8: Rheological test after 5 cycles of extrusion and injection for the PHBV-PBAT1

Figure 9: Rheological test after 5 cycles of extrusion and injection for the PHBV-StarchPBAT1

4.3 Biodegradability

Three types of test have been carried out to determine the biodegradability properties of the developed PHBV blends, specifically the mixtures of PHBV-PBAT1 and PHBV-StarchPBAT1. The first tests followed the ISO 14855-1:2012 standard for determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions — Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide. The second test following the ISO 17556:2019 standard for plastics — Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in soil by measuring the oxygen demand in a respirometer or the amount of carbon dioxide evolved. Finally, a third test was performed following the ISO 19679:2020 standard for plastics — Determination of aerobic biodegradation of non-floating plastic materials in a seawater/sediment interface by the method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide.

4.3.1 Compostability

To determine the final aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions, the standard UNE-EN ISO 14855-1:2013 has been followed. The method is based on the analysis of the carbon dioxide generated during the biodegradation process.

4.3.1.1 Test method

The test method involves exposing a representative sample of the plastic material to an inoculum derived from compost in a controlled environment. Composting is carried out in a closed container where temperature, aeration and humidity are controlled and maintained at optimal levels. During the process, microorganisms in the compost decompose the plastic material, generating carbon dioxide, water, mineral salts and new biomass.

The amount of carbon dioxide generated is measured at regular time intervals. The trend allows the determination of the percentage of biodegradation of the plastic material. The percentage of biodegradation is calculated as the ratio between the carbon dioxide generated and the maximum theoretical amount of carbon dioxide that can be produced from the plastic material.

We have used the following materials:

Reference material: TLC (thin layer chromatography) grade cellulose with a particle size less than 20 µm was used as a positive control reference material.

The apparatus was as follows:

1. Composting vessels¹: These are glass jars or bottles that allow a balanced gas purge in an upward direction. A minimum volume of 2 litres is required to meet the requirements of the method, although a smaller volume may be used for review purposes.
2. Air supply system¹: Capable of supplying each vessel with dry or water-saturated air, free of carbon dioxide, at a predetermined flow rate. This flow rate must be high enough to ensure aerobic conditions during the test.
3. Apparatus for determining carbon dioxide¹: These allow determination of carbon dioxide directly or by absorption in an alkaline solution, by determining dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC). If CO₂ is measured directly in the output air, then precise control of the air flow is required.
4. Airtight tubes¹: Used to connect the composting vessels to the air supply and carbon dioxide measurement system.
5. pH meter: To measure the pH of the inoculum and the test mixture.
6. Analytical equipment: Used to determine dry solids (at 105 °C), volatile solids (at 550 °C) and total organic carbon (TOC). Also used for elemental analysis of the test material and, if necessary, for the determination of DIC.
7. Balance: Optional, to measure the mass of the test vessels with compost and test material.
8. Analytical equipment (optional): To determine air oxygen, moisture, volatile fatty acids and total nitrogen.

The test method includes the following steps:

¹The composting vessels, the air supply system, the apparatus for determining carbon dioxide and the airtight tubers are included in the respirometer Echo from ECHO instruments, which is a device system that measures the concentration of O₂ and CO₂ in the flow through the sample under controlled conditions. Flow, temperature, pressure, humidity are also continuously measured. Software automatically calculates CO₂ production and % biodegradation.

1. Inoculum preparation: Mature compost is obtained and conditioned to ensure adequate microbial activity.
2. Test material preparation: The plastic material is characterized and prepared for testing.
3. Test start-up: Inoculum and test material are mixed in a composting vessel and subjected to controlled conditions.
4. Incubation period: Carbon dioxide production is monitored and test conditions are controlled for a given period of time.
5. Test termination: The test is stopped and the results are analyzed.

4.3.1.2 Expression of results

Calculation of the theoretical amount of carbon dioxide:

The theoretical amount of carbon dioxide ($ThCO_2$), in grams per container, that can be produced by the test material is calculated using Equation 1:

$$ThCO_2 = M_{TOT} \times C_{TOT} \times \frac{44}{12} \text{ Equation 1}$$

Where:

M_{TOT} are the total dry solids, in grams, in the test material introduced into the composting vessels at the beginning of the test.

C_{TOT} is the proportion of total organic carbon in the total dry solids in the test material, in grams per gram.

Calculation of the percentage of biodegradation:

The percentage of biodegradation (D_t) of the test material is calculated for each measurement interval using Equation 2:

$$D_t = \frac{CO_{2T} - CO_{2B}}{ThCO_2} \times 100 \text{ Equation 2}$$

Where:

CO_{2T} is the cumulative amount of carbon dioxide generated in each composting vessel containing the test material, in grams per vessel.

CO_{2B} is the average cumulative amount of carbon dioxide generated in the target containers, in grams per container.

The CO₂ is the theoretical amount of carbon dioxide that the test material can produce, in grams per container.

If the differences between the individual results are less than 20%, the average biodegradation percentage is calculated. If this is not the case, the values from each composting bin are used. The same equation is used to calculate the degree of biodegradability of the reference material.

4.3.1.3 Presentation of results

Measurement data and calculations are presented in tables for the test material, reference material and blanks for each measurement day. The cumulative amount of carbon dioxide generated by each vessel is plotted as a function of time. A biodegradation curve (percent biodegradation as a function of time) is also plotted for the test material and the reference material. Mean values are used if the differences between the individual values are less than 20%. If this is not the case, biodegradation curves are plotted for each composting bin.

The average degree of biodegradation is read from the stationary phase of the biodegradation curve and this value is noted as the final test result. If the test material consists of discrete pieces, the degree of disintegration of the material is described qualitatively. Additional information such as photographs or measured values of the main physical properties are added if available.

Table 6: Results of compostability test

COMPOST	CO2 (mg)	Biodegradation %	Time (day)
Cellulose	94123	87,3	80
PHBV+PBAT	150247	78,9	80
PHBV+starchPBAT	165974	81,3	80

Figure 10: cumulative amount of carbon dioxide generated for the blends in compost

Figure 11: percent biodegradation of the blends in compost as a function of time

The two materials tested, both the PHBV+PBAT mixture and the PHBV+Starch PBAT mixture, are compostable according to UNE-EN ISO 14855-1. Both materials show a degree of biodegradation of less than 20% difference with respect to the reference material.

4.3.1.4 *Validity of results*

(a) The degree of biodegradation of the reference material must be greater than 70% after 45 days.

b) The difference between the percentage of biodegradation of the reference material in the different composting vessels must be less than 20% at the end of the test.

c) The inoculum in the blank must have generated more than 50 mg but less than 150 mg of carbon dioxide per gram of volatile solids (average values) after 10 days of incubation.

If these criteria are not met, the assay is considered invalid and must be repeated.

4.3.2 *Biodegradability in soil*

In order to determine the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in soil, the standard UNE-EN ISO 17556 has been followed. The method consists of mixing the plastic material with soil and placing the mixture in a respirometer or in a system for measuring the amount of carbon dioxide released.

The level of biodegradation is calculated by comparing the oxygen demand or the amount of carbon dioxide released with the theoretical amount. The normal test period is six months, but it can be shortened or lengthened until a plateau phase is reached. However, the test must not exceed two years.

4.3.2.1 *Materials*

The following materials were used:

1. Distilled water, containing less than 2 mg DOC per liter.
2. Carbon dioxide absorbent, preferably soda lime tablets.
3. Test material: Natural and/or synthetic polymers, copolymers or mixtures thereof; plastic materials containing additives such as plasticizers or colorants; water-soluble polymers. Must be of known mass and contain

sufficient carbon to produce a BOD or an amount of carbon dioxide that can be adequately measured by the analytical equipment used.

4. Reference material: A well-defined biodegradable polymer, such as microcrystalline cellulose powder, ashless cellulose filters, or poly(R)-3-hydroxybutyrate [(R)-PHB].
5. Test soil: A natural soil or a standardized soil.

4.3.2.2 Apparatus

The apparatus was as follows:

1. Enclosed respirometer, including test flasks and all necessary equipment, placed in an enclosure at constant temperature or in a thermostatic apparatus (e.g., in a water bath).
2. Apparatus for measuring the amount of carbon dioxide released:
3. Test flasks: glass vessels (e.g., conical flasks or bottles), equipped with a tube impermeable to carbon dioxide to allow purging with gas, and placed in an enclosure at constant temperature or in a thermostatic apparatus (e.g., in a water bath).
4. CO₂-free air production system, capable of producing a CO₂-free air flow rate of several ml/min in each test flask, remaining constant between $\pm 10\%$.
5. Analytical instrument for the accurate determination of carbon dioxide.
6. Analytical balance.
7. pH meter.

4.3.2.3 Principle of the method

The plastic material is mixed with soil and incubated in a closed respirometer or in a system for measuring the amount of carbon dioxide released. Biodegradability is determined from monitoring and comparing the oxygen demand or the amount of carbon dioxide released with respect to the theoretical amount.

4.3.2.4 Operating procedure

1. Preparation of test material: A known mass of plastic material containing sufficient carbon to produce a BOD or a quantity of carbon dioxide that can be adequately measured is used. The ThOD or ThCO₂ is calculated from the

chemical formula or determined by means of a suitable analytical technique. The quantity of test material must be sufficient to compensate for any variation in the development of oxygen consumption or any carbon dioxide released from the test soil.

2. Preparation of reference material: A well-defined biodegradable polymer is used as the reference material.
3. Preparation of test soil: A natural soil or a standardized soil is used. The soil is sifted to obtain particles less than 5 mm in size. Plants, stones and other inert materials are removed. The water content and pH of the soil are adjusted.
4. Set up and run the test: Prepare three test flasks for the test material, three flasks for the blank control, three flasks to check soil activity using a reference material, and if required, one flask to check for possible abiotic degradation or non-biological changes in the test material and one flask to check for any possible inhibitory effects of the test material. Place soil in the bottom of each flask and add the test material or reference material. Place the flasks in a constant temperature environment and allow the flasks to reach the desired temperature. Make all necessary connections to the respirometer or CO₂-free air production system and begin incubation. Take any necessary manometer readings or check that the oxygen consumption recorder is working properly. Measure the amount of carbon dioxide released from each flask.

4.3.2.5 *Expression of results*

The percentage of biodegradation of the test material has been calculated using equations 3 and 4 for carbon dioxide released. The measured carbon dioxide amounts and the percentage of biodegradation values for each point in time that the measurements were made are compiled and tabulated. The curve of carbon dioxide released as a function of time and a curve of percentage biodegradation as a function of time are plotted.

$$ThCO_2 = \frac{44}{12} x m x w_c \text{ Equation 3}$$

Where:

$ThCO_2$ is the carbon content of the test material, determined from the chemical formula or from elemental analysis, expressed as a mass fraction.

m is the mass of the test material, in milligrams, introduced into the test system.

w_c is the carbon content of the test material, determined from the chemical formula or from elemental analysis, expressed as a mass fraction.

$$D_t = \frac{\Sigma m_T - \Sigma m_B}{ThCO_2} \text{ Equation 4}$$

Where:

Σm_T is the amount of carbon dioxide, in milligrams, released into the test flask FT between the start of the test and time t .

Σm_B is the amount of carbon dioxide, in milligrams, released into the FB control blank flask between the start of the test and time t .

$ThCO_2$ is the theoretical amount of carbon dioxide, in milligrams, released by the test material.

The percentage of biodegradation of the reference material in the FC soil activity test flask is calculated in the same way.

Table 7: Results of biodegradability in soil

Sample in SOIL	CO2 (mg)	Biodegradation %	Time (day)
Cellulose	97900	87	250
PHBV+PBAT	137400	72	250
PHBV+starchPBAT	143256	77	250

Figure 12: cumulative amount of carbon dioxide generated for the blends in soil

Figure 13: percent biodegradation of the blends in soil as a function of time

The two materials tested, both the PHBV+PBAT mixture and the PHBV+Starch PBAT mixture, are compostable according to the UNE-EN ISO 17556 standard. Both materials show a degree of biodegradation with respect to the reference material of less than 20% difference. The degree of biodegradation of the reference material was higher than 60% in the plateau phase.

4.3.2.6 Validity of results

The test is considered valid if the degree of biodegradation of the reference material is more than 60% in the plateau phase or at the end of the test and the carbon dioxide amounts released from the three FB blanks are within 20% of the

average in the plateau phase or at the end of the test. From these criteria, the test outcomes were valid.

4.3.3 Biodegradability in seawater

In order to determine the aerobic biodegradability of non-floating plastic materials at a seawater/sediment interface, the UNE-EN ISO 19679:2021 standard has been followed. The method is based on the determination of CO₂ released in a system simulating the seawater/sediment interface. The plastic material is placed in a closed flask with sandy marine sediment and seawater, and the amount of CO₂ released during microbial degradation is measured.

4.3.3.1 Materials

The following materials were used: distilled or deionized water, artificial seawater (prepared with salts such as sodium chloride, magnesium chloride, etc.), natural seawater and sandy sediment.

4.3.3.2 Apparatus

1. Enclosed respirometer², including test flasks and all necessary equipment, placed in an enclosure at constant temperature or in a thermostatic apparatus (e.g., in a water bath).
2. Apparatus for measuring the amount of carbon dioxide released:
3. Test flasks: glass vessels (e.g., conical flasks or bottles), equipped with a tube impermeable to carbon dioxide to allow purging with gas, and placed in an enclosure at constant temperature or in a thermostatic apparatus (e.g., in a water bath).
4. CO₂-free air production system, capable of producing a CO₂-free air flow rate of several ml/min in each test flask, remaining constant between $\pm 10\%$.
5. Analytical instrument for the accurate determination of carbon dioxide.
6. Analytical balance.

²The composting vessels, the air supply system, the apparatus for determining carbon dioxide and the airtight tubers are included in the respirometer Echo from ECHO instruments, which is a device system that measures the concentration of O₂ and CO₂ in the flow through the sample under controlled conditions. Flow, temperature, pressure, humidity are also continuously measured. Software automatically calculates CO₂ production and % biodegradation.

7. pH meter.

4.3.3.3 Test procedure

The test procedure is divided into several parts:

1. Preparation of test material: plastic material is cut into disc shape and its total organic carbon (TOC) content is calculated.
2. Preparation of the reference material: Ash-free cellulose filters are used as reference material and a non-biodegradable polymer is used as a negative control.
3. Sediment preparation: The sediment is filtered to remove excess seawater.
4. Test set-up: Several flasks are prepared with test material, blanks, reference material and negative control.
5. Pre-conditioning phase: Sediment and seawater are incubated in the flasks to reduce excess organic matter.
6. Start of the test: Test material, reference material and negative control are placed in the corresponding flasks.
7. Carbon dioxide measurement: CO₂ released has been quantitatively measured with a method based on infrared CO₂ analyzers.
8. End of test: The test ends when a constant level of CO₂ release is reached.

4.3.3.4 Calculation and Expression of Results

The amount of CO₂ produced is calculated by correcting the measured values from the test flasks with those values from the blanks. The percentage of biodegradation is calculated as the ratio between the amount of CO₂ released and the theoretical amount of CO₂ (ThCO₂), which is determined from the TOC of the material.

Biodegradation percentage:

The percentage of biodegradation (%B) is calculated using Equation 5.

$$\%B = \frac{CO_2}{ThCO_2} \times 100 \text{ Equation 5}$$

where CO₂ is the amount of CO₂ produced (in mg) and ThCO₂ is the theoretical amount of CO₂. This theoretical amount is calculated with Equation 6:

$$ThCO_2 = S \times TOC (\%) \times \frac{44}{12} \text{ Equation 6}$$

Where S is the amount of test material (in mg), TOC is the total organic carbon content of the material (%), 44 is the molecular mass of CO₂ and 12 is the molecular mass of carbon.

4.3.3.5 Interpretation of Results

The results are plotted in graphs showing the amount of CO₂ released and the percentage of biodegradation as a function of time. The maximum level of biodegradation was determined from the stationary phase of the biodegradation curve, which occurs when the CO₂ release reaches a plateau value. It is important to note that the shape and wettability of the material can influence the results, so the method is best suited for comparing materials of similar chemical structure.

Table 8: Results of biodegradability in marine environment

MARINE ENVIRONMENT	CO2 (mg)	Biodegradation %	Time (day)
Cellulose	129,8	78,3	250
PHBV+PBAT	117	57	250
PHBV+starchPBAT	145	69	250

Figure 14: cumulative amount of carbon dioxide generated for the blends in seawater

Figure 15: percent biodegradation of the blends in seawater as a function of time

Despite the necessary long duration of these tests carried out in seawater, biodegradability of the PHBV-StarchPBAT mixture in this medium was demonstrated. The PHBV-PBAT mixture also came close to achieving this standard for biodegradability. With a higher PHBV content, it is expected that the PHBV-PBAT would have also been within the standard of biodegradability.

4.3.3.6 Validity of Results

For the test results to be valid, the following criteria must be met:

The biodegradation rate of the reference material must be greater than 60% after 180 days.

The amount of CO₂ released from the blanks at the end of the test must not exceed 3.5 mg CO₂/g wet sediment after 6 months.

The amount of CO₂ released from the three blanks should be within 20% of the mean in the stationary phase or at the end of the test.

The difference between the percentage of biodegradation of the reference material in the different vessels must be less than 20% of the mean at the end of the test.

The percentage of biodegradation of the negative control must be less than 10% at the end of the test.

If these criteria are not met, the test should be repeated using another sediment.

5 Conclusions

It was found that the developed PHV based formulations, with biodegradable polymers such as PBAT and a mixture of starch and PBAT (PHBV-PBAT1 and PHBV-StarchPBAT1), can undergo five recycling cycles without significant loss of important mechanical and rheological properties. This outcome was demonstrated by processing the mixtures five consecutive times by extrusion and injection molding. The, establishing the recyclability of the materials was established.

The developed formulations have been furthermore tested for:

1. compostability according to UNE EN ISO 14855,
2. biodegradability in soil according to UNE EN ISO 17556, and
3. biodegradability in seawater according to UNE EN ISO 19679.

The material compostability and biodegradability was confirmed. The developed formulations with PHBV are compostable and also biodegradable in soil and seawater. Only the PHBV-PBAT formulation did not quite comply with the UNE EN ISO 19679 standard by a small margin. However, based on the biodegradation trends it is expected, nevertheless, that if the test time could have been extended then the standard would have been reached for this specific PHBV-PBAT formulation. Unfortunately, the test time was limited due to the project execution time.

